

Study of binary systems inducing mesophase and determination of latent transition temperature

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Manuscript received 28 January 1999, revised 30 August 1999, accepted 3 March 2000

Five binary systems consisting of common component as nematogen (A), viz. *p*-(*p*'-*n*-propyloxybenzoyloxy)anisole is mixed with un-common component (B) (nonmesogen or monotropic nematic), *para*-substituted Schiff bases, viz. $X-C_6H_4-CH=N-C_6H_4-Y$, where $X = CH_3, Cl, OCH_3$ and $Y = OCH_3$ or OC_2H_5 . Interesting results are obtained as (i) nematic mesophase maintained monotropically and enantiotropically from the binary systems with nonmesogen (B), (ii) smectic mesophase induced and nematic mesophase maintained from binary system comprising monotropic nematic component (B). Polarity and polarizability of terminal groups of component (B) play an important role in enhancing the liquid crystallinity. The group efficiency order is derived as, $OC_2H_5 > CH_3 = Cl$. Latent transition temperatures of components (B) for smectic and nematic mesophases are determined.

Several binary systems have been studied earlier¹⁻⁶ with a view to understand the effect of terminal groups on liquid crystallinity in a mixed melt and to determine latent transition temperature (LTT) of components (B). Here we report such studies on five binary systems consisting of *p*-(*p*'-*n*-propyloxybenzoyloxy)anisole as component (A) and *para*-substituted Schiff bases $X-C_6H_4-CH=N-C_6H_4-Y$ ($X = CH_3, Cl, OCH_3$; $Y = OCH_3, OC_2H_5$) as component (B).

Results and Discussion

The transition temperatures of pure components and binary mixtures as well as mole % and temperatures of eutectic point and triple point as derived from phase diagrams are recorded in Table 1. Latent transition temperatures determined from the phase diagrams are recorded in Table 2. The composition and temperature range over which mesophase appears depend upon the degree of similarity of constituent components (A and B) of a binary system in shape, size, polarity of terminal groups and polarizability. The constituent components of all the binary systems are elongated lath-like and structurally similar. Therefore, favourable cohesive intermolecular forces of attraction, conducive to mesophase formation operates over wider range of composition as shown in Table 3.

The minimum proportion of composition required to disrupt completely the mesomorphic alignments of component (A) in a mixed melt are 94.0, 94.5, 100.0, 80.0 and 85.0 mole % of (B), respectively, for nematic mesophase. Thus the disruption caused by nonmesogenic components (B) is in the expected order of the polarity of terminal groups. Though, CH_3 and Cl terminals are equally compatible, however, minimum proportion of component (B) needed to disrupt mesomorphic alignments in a mixed melt

are 94.0 and 80.0 mole % as well as 94.5 and 85.0 mole %, respectively. This is due to the difference in melting points of Schiff bases 1 and 4 as well as 2 and 5, respectively. Schiff base 3 shows nematic mesophase persistence over the entire range of composition because component-B itself is monotropic nematic. But smectic mesophase is induced between 21.0 and 90.0 mole % of (A). This is because of the polarity of OCH_3 terminal group being more compared to CH_3 and Cl terminal group at the left (X) keeping OC_2H_5 terminal unchanged at the right (Y). Polarity concept is further supported by initial slope values of the nematic isotropic liquid transition curves which is the characteristic of components (B).

Initial slope obtained (Table 4) has been accepted as having additive effect due to the two polar terminal groups (X and Y). If the contribution of CH_3 or Cl group to the initial slope value is taken⁷ as 7 for nematic mesophase, then the 'group slope' value for OCH_3 group in binary systems 1 and 4 are 1.5 and similarly for OC_2H_5 group the slope values are 1.0 or 1.25. Using the value of OC_2H_5 , the group slope value for OCH_3 in binary system 3 is $3.0-1.25 = 1.75$. Thus group slope value for CH_3, Cl, OCH_3 and OC_2H_5 terminals are 7.0, 7.0, 1.5 or 1.75, and 1.0 or 1.25, respectively. Thus the order of group slope values and hence the order of polarity or group efficiency for nematic mesophase of terminal groups can be expressed as

$$OC_2H_5 > OCH_3 > CH_3 = Cl \\ (1.0 \text{ or } 1.25) (1.5 \text{ or } 1.75) \quad (7.0)$$

This is in good agreement with the previous work⁶. The constituent components of all the five binary systems are geometrically rod-like and structurally resembles each

Table 1. Transition temperatures of binary systems

Sl no	Component (B)		Type of mesophase	Mole % of component (A)																	Eutectic point		Triple point	
	X	Y		0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	Temp °C	Mole %	Temp °C	Mole %						
1	CH ₃	OCH ₃	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-					
			Nematic	-	(61.5)	(67.0)	70.0	64.5	73.0	78.0	80.5	83.0	86.0	90.0	64.0	38.5	72.0	28.0						
			Isotropic	88.0	84.0	78.0	73.5	84.5	95.5	100.0	100.0	103.0	107.0	116.0	-	-	-	-						
2	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-					
			Nematic	-	-	(85.5)	(77.0)	85.0	74.5	74.0	79.0	82.0	85.5	90.0	71.0	54.5	89.5	35.5						
			Isotropic	108.5	108.0	102.5	94.5	90.0	93.5	96.5	99.0	102.0	107.0	116.0	-	-	-	-						
3	OCH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	Smectic	-	-	-	-	(96.5)	81.5	76.0	75.5	77.5	81.0	85.0	-	-	-	-	97.0	31.0				
			Nematic	(121.0)	(115.0)	(108.0)	99.0	95.0	93.5	93.0	93.0	93.0	96.0	90.0	76.0	43.5	106.0	26.5						
			Isotropic	128.5	123.0	117.0	105.0	103.5	103.0	109.0	107.0	110.0	113.0	116.0	-	-	-	-						
4	Cl	OCH ₃	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
			Nematic	-	-	(80.0)	(84.0)	81.0	72.0	72.5	77.0	82.0	87.0	90.0	72.0	49.8	86.0	36.0						
			Isotropic	123.5	117.0	106.0	73.0	88.0	95.0	98.0	100.0	104.0	108.0	116.0	-	-	-	-						
5	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
			Nematic	-	-	(89.0)	(90.0)	82.0	73.5	76.0	79.0	81.0	84.0	90.0	72.0	47.5	91.0	34.5						
			Isotropic	121.5	119.0	110.0	97.0	91.5	93.0	95.0	98.0	101.5	107.5	116.0	-	-	-	-						

() Indicates monotropy

Table 2. LTT determined (°C)

Schiff base	Present investigation	Ref 2	Ref 3	Ref 4	Ref 5
1	55.0 Nm	55.0 Nm	-	-	-
2	87.0 Nm	90.0 Nm	-	-	-
3	111.0 Sm	-	-	-	-
4	72.5 Nm	73.0 Nm	-	-	-
5	86.0 Nm	86.0 Nm	90.0	87.0	86.5

Table 3.

Sl no	Schiff base (B) mixed with component (A)		Range of composition over which mesophase appears in terms of mole % of A
	X	Y	
1	CH ₃	OCH ₃	6.0-100.0 Nematic
2	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	5.5-100.0 Nematic
3*	OCH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	0.0-100.0 Nematic 21.0-90.0 Smectic
4	Cl	OCH ₃	20.0-100.0 Nematic
5	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	15.0-100.0 Nematic

* Monotropic nematic component (B)

Table 4.

Component (B) Schiff base	Initial Slope °C/mole% × 10
1	8.5
2	8.0
3	3.0
4	8.5
5	8.25

other. Therefore, π -electron system of aromatic rings being polarizable permitting conjugative interactions and terminal polar end-groups of rod-shaped molecules in which dipole moment acting across the long molecular axis in a mixed melt give rise to strong intermolecular attraction which are anisotropics and hence stabilises the ordered arrangement of the molecules. The nonmesogenic Schiff base components in binary systems 1, 2, 4 and 5 maintains parallel orientation of the molecules in a mixed melt resulting nematic mesophase which in case of binary system 3, the monotropic nematic component stabilises nematic mesophase and smectic mesophase. The presence of OCH₃ group instead of CH₃ or Cl terminal at the left end of the molecule with OC₂H₅ as common right terminal, the smectic mesophase is induced enantiotropically and monotropically within sufficient range of temperature and composition. The unlike constituent molecules in a homogenous mixed melt do exhibit layered arrangement and the layers are free to slide over one another within 21-90 mole % of (A) giving rise to the induced smectic mesophase, with enantiotropic and monotropic nematic mesophase at higher or lower temperatures, respectively.

The mole % of component (A) are plotted against the transition temperatures. The curves of the nematic isotropic transition temperature or vice versa and smectic nematic

transition temperature or vice versa in phase diagrams of binary systems (Figs. 1-5) are extrapolated to 0.0 mole % of (A); the LTTs for nematic and smectic mesophases are determined indicating potential to exhibit nematic or smectic mesophase. The LTT of component (A) is determined

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Fig 5

for smectic mesophase formation by extrapolating smectic-nematic transition curve to 100 mole % of (A) The value obtained is 101.0°. The values of LTTs as determined from present investigation are recorded in Table 2 and compared favourably with the previous work²

Experimental

Component (A) of binary systems was prepared by condensing *p*-propyloxybenzoyl chloride⁸ with *p*-hydroxy-anisole. The product was purified and crystallised from alcohol. Schiff bases were prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of corresponding aldehydes and amines in alcohol on a water-bath and crystallised from alcohol.

Melting point and other physical data are comparable with the reported values. The transition temperatures were observed under a Leitz Laborlux 12 POL polarising microscope with Kofler heating stage.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. A. Vora and Prof. Uma Chudasama, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University, Baroda, for their valuable cooperation.

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